

Deliverable D7.1

Project Visual Identity & Templates

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1. Executive Summary

This document describes the objectives, structure, and look and feel of the IP4MaaS visual identity and templates. The visual identity is an essential means for the IP4MaaS project to reach its objectives concerning communication, as well as strengthening the project's identity and positioning IP4MaaS as a strong brand.

2. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
CFM	Calls for Members
DL	Dissemination and exploitation leader
DoA	Description of the Action
EL	Ethical leader
EU	European Union
FS	Financial Statement
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
OC	Open Call
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
QAC	Quality Assurance Committee
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
TL	Technical leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work package leader

3. Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable 7.1 “Project Visual Identity & Templates” in the framework of task 7.1 of the IP4MaaS project (S2R-OC-IP4-01-2020).

4. Objective/Aim

The objectives of the IP4MaaS communication and dissemination activities are to raise awareness and disseminate project developments to key stakeholders, to ensure maximal exploitation of project results, to organise key project events, and finally to implement and update an appropriate online presence (website, social media).

The IP4MaaS visual identity and templates are important tools to reach these goals. The project logo and an accompanying visual identity (colour scheme, fonts) have been developed to establish a strong project identity. A strong identity evokes recognition among stakeholders, ensures consistency in communication activities, and gives the IP4MaaS project as a strong brand. The project logo will be used in many ways throughout the project: it will be visible on the project website, on the project leaflet, in presentation templates, and on all other forms of communication material developed by the IP4MaaS project.

5. IP4MaaS Visual identity

5.1. IP4MaaS Logo

The IP4MaaS logo was developed by a graphic designer after a dedicated briefing about the project. The logo was launched in January 2021.

In accordance with the project partners and following advice from the graphic designer, an innovative colour scheme has been chosen for the project, deviating from the more traditional combination of colours that are often used for projects, such as green and blue. This has been done to embody the innovative nature of the project. Furthermore, one of the main colours of the logo is orange, which has been chosen to stay close to the main colour of the Shift2MaaS logo, which can be considered the predecessor of IP4MaaS.

The design of the logo has been chosen to reflect the main topic of the project, namely Mobility as a Service. The line going through the words 'IP 4 MaaS' resembles a journey or route, with the positioned dots depicting stops or modes, depending on interpretation. By looking at the logo, it is clear the project is about travelling in a dynamic way. All partners express their opinion about the logo and agreed on the final version to be used.

Figure 1: IP4MaaS logo

5.2. IP4MaaS Graphic Charter

In addition to the IP4MaaS logo, a dedicated graphic charter has been developed, stating the fonts and colours to be used when creating visual materials for the IP4MaaS project. The charter can be found in Annex 1.

5.3. IP4MaaS website and Social Media

The IP4MaaS visual identity will be utilised for both the IP4MaaS website and IP4MaaS Twitter account. The Twitter account has been launched early May 2021 (handle: @IP4MaaS_EU) and the website will be launched late May 2021 (address: www.ip4maas.eu).

Both channels will be further elaborated in D7.2 'Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Activities', due in May 2021.

6. IP4MaaS templates

To ensure consistent use of the IP4MaaS logo and colours, a PowerPoint template has been developed, as well as document templates (a deliverable template, a meeting minutes template, and a meeting agenda template) that follow the Shift2Rail handbook with the standard guidelines. All consortium partners are strongly encouraged to make use of these templates when presenting the IP4MaaS project in internal or external meetings.

For the PowerPoint template, three different covers have been designed. This way, partners can adjust their cover of choice according to the event IP4MaaS is being presented at.

The IP4MaaS PowerPoint template, as well as the Minutes of Meeting, Meeting Agenda and Deliverable Templates can be found in Annex 2.

7. Conclusions

By developing a logo, visual identity and templates at an early stage in the project, an essential step towards a coherent and consistent project identity has been made. By consistently using the IP4MaaS logo and visual identity, the project will gain recognition among relevant stakeholders and become a solid brand.

8. Appendices

Annex 1: IP4MaaS Graphic Charter

GRAPHIC CHARTER

IP4MaaS

! Use it on white background only

Yellow Skylight
Web: #FAB300
RGB: 250 / 179 / 0
CMJN: 0 / 34 / 96 / 0

Sunset Pink
Web: #E16876
RGB: 225 / 104 / 118
CMJN: 0 / 70 / 37 / 7

Orange Island
Web: #EB8D5D
RGB: 235 / 141 / 93
CMJN: 0 / 53 / 64 / 4

Grey Mountain
Web: #706F6F
RGB: 112 / 111 / 111
CMJN: 0 / 0 / 0 / 70

Designer Font: Houschka Rounded
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo conse-

Replacement Font: Source Sans pro
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis

Annex 2: IP4MaaS Document templates

a) PowerPoint Template

Title

Subtitle

Title

Subtitle

- Body text
- Body text

Thank you for your attention!

www.website.eu

Name

emailaddress@email.com

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b) Meeting Agenda Template & Minutes of Meeting Template

Meeting Agenda
Topic/title of meeting

Project:	IP4MaaS	Date/Time:	dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm-hh:mm
Meeting Type:	Type	Location:	Room
Meeting Coordinator:	Name	Issue Date:	dd/mm/yyyy

Time	Agenda Items	Speaker
	Item 1	Speaker 1
	Item 2	Speaker 2
	Item 3	Speaker 3

Minutes of Meeting

Topic/title of meeting

Project:	Title	Date/Time:	dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm-hh:mm
Meeting Type:	Type	Location:	Room
Meeting Coordinator:	Name	Issue Date:	dd/mm/yyyy

Attendee Name (<i>present</i>)	Initials	Organisation
First Name, Last Name	FL	Organisation
First Name, Last Name	FL	Organisation
First Name, Last Name	FL	Organisation

Meeting Agenda	Speaker
1. Item 1	1. Speaker 1
2. Item 2	2. Speaker 2
3. Item 2	3. Speaker 3

Summary of Meeting	
Topic	Summary
Item 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">NoteNoteNote
Item 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none">NoteNoteNote
Item 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none">NoteNoteNote

Action nr.	Action	Related Topic	Due date	Action Owner
1	- Description of action	Topic 1	Dd/mm/yy	Name

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c) Cover of Deliverable Template

Deliverable D X.Y
Deliverable title

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